

Propagating and preserving Havēlī Music through the internet - A study

Chaitra Sontakke

Research Scholar, Jain (Deemed to be) University,
Bengaluru

Dr. Arati N Rao

Adjunct Professor, Jain (Deemed to be) University,
Bengaluru

Abstract

Havēlī Saṅgīta is a specialised form of music of the Puṣṭi Mārga tradition founded by Śrī Vallabhācārya, performed at the Vaiṣṇava temples of north, west and central India. The musical and compositional style is Dhruvapada. The musical compositions of Havēlī Saṅgīta, set in specific rāga-s and tāla-s are sung accompanying the worship or sēva performed during the day. Havēlī Saṅgīta comprising precomposed as well as improvisational music, has been handed down through oral tradition over the years. The practitioners of the authentic form are few in number. During the pandemic period, a few musicians of this tradition have used the internet, particularly social media, for performance, archiving and teaching music. The present study aims to analyse the effectiveness of the internet in preserving and propagating Havēlī Saṅgīta. The methodology is qualitative, descriptive and exploratory. The data for this study comprises internet archival recordings and interviews with experts. Key findings of the study are: authentic features of Havēlī Saṅgīta have been mostly preserved, while some adaptations are also seen.

Key words: Havēlī Saṅgīta, temple music, music performance, pedagogy, archive, online

Research Paper

Introduction

Havēlī Saṅgīta is the modern name given to the Puṣṭi Mārgīya Saṅgīta on the platform of All India Radio. The classical music traditions of Dhruvad and Khayal that are in practice today trace their roots to the musical tradition of the Puṣṭi Mārgīya musical tradition of the Aṣṭa Chāpa Kavī. Aṣṭa Chāpa is a congregation of eight saint poet musicians initiated into the Puṣṭi Mārga tradition by Śrī Vallabhācārya and his son Śrī Viṭṭhalnāthji. Though the practitioners are few, Havēlī Saṅgīta is a continuing tradition that has stood the test of time.

This study aims at examining how the Havēlī Saṅgīta tradition has created its presence in the contemporary world of music consumption through internet- the social media in particular. The study takes into account the following aspects—

- pedagogy followed in the teaching videos
- the music performances
- knowledge sharing: documentation and archival

This study discusses further steps that could be taken in order to enhance the process of knowledge transfer and archival of the musical style and a living tradition like the Havēlī Saṅgīta.

Review of literature

Based on the aims that have been set for this study the following works have been shortlisted and a brief summary has been given.

1. Bindu, K. “Impact of technology in Music”, 2003.

This thesis includes various facets such as Performance, teaching–tools used in the classroom, for practice and for recording, role of popular media, preservation and voice techniques. Students from different parts of the world learn music from their homes.(Bindu, 32). There is a brief mention of internet being an interactive platform where an artist could upload material; Skype is also available to the user (Bindu, 215)

2. Vedabala, Samidha. ‘Indian Classical Music in a Globalized World’ Sangeet Galaxy, Vol.5, Issue-1, (January 2016) pp. 3-9

This article discusses the influences of globalisation on the traditional art form like classical music and takes a critical approach to learning and performances that are carried out using the on-line medium.

3. Das, Shambhavi. 'Role of media and technology in Indian Classical Music' <https://www.academia.edu/32848113>

This article touches upon the possibility of using various technological tools for teaching and the live sessions that facilitate learning and certification through Skype and Google hangout.

4. Ravishankar, Sudha. Banerjee, Neil. 'An analysis of audience engagement by Indian Classical Music artists and dancers during lockdown via social media' Gap Bodhi Taru, a Global Journal of Humanities, Volume IV, Issue- III (September 2021) pp. 31-5

This article assesses the performer-audience relationship and how Indian Classical Music and Dance has kept up in pace with the growing technology and the advent of social media through smartphones.

Research gap

The review of literature provides a overview of the influence of technology and internet on classical music performances touching upon the learning. The specific genres have not been highlighted. The present study takes a deep dive into the specific online teaching methods of Havēlī music, performance videos, and knowledge-sharing sessions.

Methodology and Scope

The methodology followed is qualitative, descriptive and exploratory. The scope of this study is restricted to the recordings of Pt. Śrī Goswami Gokulotsav Maharaj and Śrī Krishnadas Nayak.

Analysis has been done by selecting sample videos from a set of teaching videos, videos of recorded performances and live videos that are available in the public domain. The analysis takes into account the interviews of expert practitioners of Havēlī Saṅgīta. The sample analysis has been carried out by the selection of videos from the series called 'Aao Kīrtan Seekhe' by Sri Krishnadas Nayak on the YouTube channel titled as 'Pushtivrund'. The recorded performance videos and live performance and demonstration videos of the two artists have been considered.

The following are the parameters for analysis- the rāga svarūpa or rāga characteristics, the tāla or the rhythm cycle, the rendering style of the pada or composition,

the improvisational aspects and the skill development (pertaining to the area of pedagogy), the cultural background of the composition rendered.

Analysis

The analysis carried out with each of the above mentioned parameters is followed by discussion. The discussion brings forth the objectives achieved through the medium of internet and points out at the limitations that are encountered.

Pedagogical aspects

Teaching videos-Composition

The video Aao Kīrtan Seekhe: S1|E5|| Raag: Sorath, starts with an explanation of the significance of Rāga Sōraṭh in the Puṣṭi Mārga tradition along with the introduction of the rāga svarūpa or form. The accompanying instruments used are the Bānsuri and the Pakhāvāj. The following points are drawn from this teaching video:

1. Rāga Sōraṭh is performed from Jyēṣṭha śuddha pūrṇimā to Ratha yātra time period.
2. The theoretical description of this rāga has been displayed on the screen while the rāga āroha-avaroha and the key phrases of the rāga is being performed (Pushtivrund, 1:01 to 1:58 min). The description in text form includes the rāga characteristics like what are the types of svara-s used, the Thāt under which this rāga is classified, the subtle difference between this rāga and another rāga with similar notational structure. In this example, how rāga Des is different from Sōraṭh has been mentioned.
3. The composition is accompanied by harmonium played by the singer himself. The Pakhāvāj is electronic since this video was shot during the pandemic.
4. The words being sung are displayed on the screen in Devanāgarī and English.
5. The screen forms the backdrop with different paintings depicting the Kṛṣṇa themes that are described in the words of the pada or composition.
6. The first pada is 'Dekh ri Naval Nanda Kishore' set to Taal Tevra and the second pada is 'Maiya mori Kavar kaun lei' set to Tritāl.
7. The Tāla Bōl of Tāla Tevrā of 7 mātṛā-s is provided in the form of a table with indications of tālī and khālī or clap and wave signs within the rhythm cycle. The distribution into 3 vibhāga-s with 3,2,2 mātṛā-s in each part is shown in the Tāla script provided.

8. The Tāla table for Tritāl is provided with the Bōl, the mātrā-s, the indications of tāli, khāli and the distribution of mātrā-s into 4 vibhāga-s with 2 mātrā-s each. From the Tāla table provided it is evident that Tritāl is of 8 mātrā-s in the Havēlī Saṅgīta tradition. It is mentioned in the introduction that this composition starts from the 5th mātrā.
9. The composition is adorned with certain intricate gamaka-s; For instance in the composition Dekh ri Naval Nand Kisora, in the Antara Śravaṇa Dhvani (Pushṭivrund, 4:50minutes), the following gamaka-s that combine āndōlan and sphurita are sung- R-P M-D PDṆ - Ṇ D P, MD PD P MP DP D - M - R, NŚRŚ R Ṇ D. Along with these phrases swift movement like MP NŚ RĠ R- Ṇ D - is sung.

More features of the musical style have been discussed and demonstrated in different videos in this series. In the season-2 videos, there are two students' voices following the teacher's voice, thus demonstrating using the sing and repeat methodology for teaching. The singing pitch chosen in this set is B flat, which is natural and comfortable pitch for learners singing in these videos and most learners.

Teaching video: Improvisational elements and cultural background

In the video, Aao Kirtan Seekhe: S1|E6|| Raag: Malhar, the significance of Rāga Malhār is stated and an explanation about the improvisation of the rāga before the commencement of the pada composition is found. The following points are drawn from this explanation:

1. Rāga Sōraṭh Malhār is performed during the time of Ratha Yātra.
2. Though the musical style is that of Dhrupad, the nom-tom ālāpa is not performed.
3. Ālāpacārī is done when the Lord is seated in preparation for the Ratha Yātra, using the words that comprise of the name of the form of the deity or sévya rūpa (of Kṛṣṇa)
4. For example: Śrī Girirāja Dharana Dhīravara lāḍilo lalanavara gāyīye, Ānaṇda ke nidhi Śrī Mathurādhiśa Śrī Naṭavaralāla Śyāmalāla lāḍilo lalanavara gāyīye, Braja ke jīvanadhana lāḍilo lalanavara gāyīye
5. The importance of words and the relevance of the performance in the prescribed sēvā krama-the order in which the rituals are performed is highlighted.

6. The different types of Malhār-s that are performed in the Puṣṭi Mārgīya sēvā krama tradition are listed out- Sōraṭh Malhār, Gauḍ Malhār, Dhūliyā Malhār, Naṭ Malhār, Sūr Malhār.

Teaching videos: Aspects of Tāla and accompaniment on the percussion

In the video Aao Kirtan Seekhe: S1|E7|| Learn how to play Jhaanjh- technique to play Tāla-s Tevrā and Choutāla on Jhānj has been demonstrated in a medium and faster speed.

In the video Aao Kirtan Seekhe: S1|E8|| Basic information of Taal Tevra and Chautal- the Tāla Bōl of Tevra and Cautāl are demonstrated on the Pakhāvaj in madhya laya tempo and the fast tempo played during the concluding part of the festival performances. This process of performing in faster tempo, called Calati has also been demonstrated as a clapping pattern using palms.

Demonstration of Tāla-s Tritāl, Dhamār and Jhaptāl have been covered in this set.

Teaching using video conferencing

Teaching of Havēlī Saṅgīta online has a factor of convenience of teaching from any location. This would be effective for learners who are of the nature of perseverance as well as an inclination towards this tradition. (Nayak Krishnadas)

Objectives achieved by the teaching-learning process through internet

1. The structure of the rāga emerges with clarity through the demonstration of the ārōha-avarōha, the key phrases of the rāga and the short ālāp that precedes the composition.
2. The vocalised syllables of the Tāla, the Tāla Bol provided in a tabular form displays with clarity the rhythm structure present within the Tāla cycle.
3. The demonstration of this set of Bol on the Pakhāvaj and Jhānj gives an insight into the correlation of these Tāla Bol syllables to the sound of the two main percussion instruments used.
4. In addition to the core knowledge of tāla essential for a performing vocalist, the learner receives exposure to the playing technique of the Jhānj that could be further practiced by the learner.
5. The necessary aid for visual learning is provided by (a) the display of the script with rāga details alongside the demonstration of rāga svarūpa through ālāp phrases and (b) by running a scroll

of words of the pada on the screen during the time the composition is being sung.

6. Auditory learning is enhanced by the slide bar facility empowering learners to listen to specific portions of the composition repeatedly.
7. The digital display of the Pichvāi style paintings provide a dynamic backdrop thus making effective use of this medium to create visual effects depicting stories related to the pada. This not only holds the attention of the listener but also enhances knowledge, helping the learner connect with the soul of the composition.
8. The paintings, because of the visual appeal may not only draw new audiences towards the musical form but also virtually create the cultural context.
9. With the help of video conferencing certain gaps could be filled in for learners, if the available videos are complemented with additional learning inputs through the session.

Limitations of the teaching-learning process through internet:

The limitations are discussed in order to explore the possibilities of enhancing the reach of the art form among learners through virtual teaching-learning techniques

1. The videos are designed for learners who have acquired certain vocal skills. Beginners may not be able to pick up the composition in all its beautiful elements by assimilating the vocal nuances and the finer aspects of handling the Laya and Tāla. The learners who have a basic training in classical music are benefitted.
2. The improvisational elements are limited to small variations in the repeated lines. The improvisation with Upaj Aṅg is driven by the expression conveyed by the words of the pada. The learning levels are not gauged accurately and the videos are targeted to benefit general learners.
3. Teaching improvisation is done in an interactive way. The spontaneity that aids improvisation in a face to face session is not emulated on this platform.
4. The feedback system is not incorporated in this format. The learner may need to be self reliant to assess ones own progress.
5. Video conferencing may help individual learners pursuing the journey of deep learning. Involving a group of learners to achieve co-learning is challenging.

6. The video conferencing mode helps those who have access to technology at high end. The internet needs to run flawlessly for the smooth functioning of the session. Learners who do not have access to good internet will not be benefitted by the virtual learning.

Performance aspects

Performance videos- recorded

In the video, Ari Maai Nai Nai Dharti| Raga Goud Malhar, the performance begins with a prārambhika ālāp that provides the glimpse of the rāga that the pada is set in. The accompanying instruments are violin, Pakhāvaj and Manjīra.

1. The video offers different views like- all artists in the frame, the focus switching to individual instruments at relevant instances, the visuals of digital Pichvāi art depicting a scene in the story.
2. Though pre planned, this video has captured certain elements of extempore in the performance through interactions among the performers.
3. The antara 'Dādur papihā bole' has been chosen for Layakāri with tihāi, improvisation by creating different rhythm patterns using the words of the composition that has a concluding phrase repeating three times.
4. The Upaj aṅg improvisation or the variations created by a single line of the composition is done using the phrase 'Nayi Nayi Dharati' from the sthāyī.
5. The visuals of the 'Pichvāi style paintings that depict different scenes of Brindāvan have been incorporated in the video, thus utilising the potential of this medium.

In another performance video, Gaave Ghanashyam Jamuna ke Teera| Raga Gaud Malhar, the following are observations are made:

1. A slightly different approach of improvisation is found. This is more focussed on the emotion conveyed by the words over rhythm aspects or layakāri improvisation that is an inherent feature of the Dhrupad style.
2. Within the pada subtle variations are found as the lines are repeated.
3. There are long drawn ālāpa-s using sustain on a single svāra.
4. The improvisation is weaved within the composition and is seen in the line repeats enhancing the expressions or bhāva that is

conveyed through the words of the pada or composition.

Under the title, Raagmala-Taalmala | Hindora ke pad, a special composition like the Rāga-Tāla mālā has been performed by Sri Krishnadas Nayak in the sequence- Gaud Malhār in Cautāl, Mārū in Jhaptāl, Sorath in Tevra, Mālāv in Tritāl also called Āditāl, miṣra Kāfī in drut Dhamār, Kalyāṇ in Calati, Gaud Malhār in drut Cautāl. This composition by Kalyanrayji Maharajshri is also found under the title 'Hindola Ke Pad Acharya Gokulotsavji Maharaj | Pushtimargiya Kirtan Haveli Sangeet'

Performance videos- live

Many studio spaces sprung up with the intent of arranging good video and audio facilities for musicians, who wished to do live performances. Such studios had separate audio input through mixer fed into the live stream ensuring a good audio experience to the listeners along with visuals that covered the singer and the accompanying instruments. This ensured the best possible quality experience for the audience. There is a factor of unpredictability due to the internet.

On the other hand, concert performances were pre-recorded in a similar technological set-up. Multiple cameras have been used for video. Each instrument and voice has been recorded simultaneously using different microphones rooted into a mixer. The mixer helps in clearly capturing the sonic nuances of each instrument, thus resulting in higher quality and detail for the listener. (Nayak Krishnadas)

Here, a case study of a full live concert has been taken up.

The duration of the full live concert is about 1:52 hours. The concert includes explanations. The concert focuses on Badhāi pada or compositions that are performed during celebrations. The concert starts with rāga Madhuvantī in Bhajani style followed by the prātaḥ smaraṇ composition by Śri Kumbhanadāsji based on rāga Rāmkali. The duration of each composition is about 10 minutes on an average, without additional accompaniment of a melodic instrument. The artist accompanies self on the harmonium.

The composition chosen for detailing out is Aisi Bansi Bāji (Nayak Krishnadas, 23:30 to 32:10 minutes) :

1. The performance starts with an ālāp that depicts the rāga svarūpa of rāga Brindāvani Sāraṅga.
2. The composition or the pada is performed with improvisation done using the concept of Upaj, the layakāri within the tāla structure of Cautāl, along

with application of ādōlita gamaka-s in adherence to the Dhrupada style.

3. The repeats in lines incorporate minute fine variations.
4. The last antara is repeated in Calati style and performed with the Jhānj. This is a special feature of the Havēlī kīrtan that is performed during the celebration of festivals or utsava pada-s.
5. Minor disturbances in audio are noticed in the beginning for a few minutes.
6. The overall experience is enriching to the listeners, especially during the pandemic.

Objectives achieved by the performance videos

1. The pre-recorded videos in the concert format ensure good audio quality and visual appeal.
2. Various ways of improvising the composition have been applied and demonstrated in the performance. The interaction among the artists shown using different camera angles captures the spontaneity that is a feature of a live performance.
3. The visuals in the backdrop help in enhancing the understanding of the bhāva conveyed by the pada composition.
4. Compositional forms like the Rāga-Tāla mālā unique to this tradition and the Calati performance along with Jhānj enrich the listener's repertoire.
5. The live musical performances on the different social media platforms played a significant role during the time of pandemic. At this time, the leading musicians of Havēlī Saṅgīta took up the ownership of propagating this unbroken tradition using the available mediums in the best possible manner.

Limitations of the performance videos

1. The musical form of Havēlī Saṅgīta or the Puṣṭi Mārgīya Bhakti Saṅgīta has the intrinsic quality of being offered to the Divine. This form of music accompanies various seva-s or rituals performed from dawn to dusk.
2. The duration of the performances shared online may have been planned as per the requirement of the different platforms like the YouTube, Instagram and so on.
3. In the live performance, certain technical glitches have been unavoidable. The choice of compositions caters to a larger audience joining online. The environment of the Havēlī is not recreated in the online concert.

Knowledge sharing

Interview recorded live on social media

Raga Seva of the Divine- Haveli Sangeet- the live knowledge sharing sessions in 2 parts-, conducted by Sri Ashok Mathur with Gokulotsav Maharajji brings forth the Bhakti philosophy that lies in the soul of this musical tradition, an insight into various rāga-s performed, excerpts of pada compositions, The common links with the classical music traditions of Dhrupad and Khayal.

Interview recorded and shared on social media

The interviews recorded by the Prasar Bharati for Doordarshan and other organisations have been shared on social media platforms like the YouTube.

Personal Interviews

Personal interviews are done by video conferencing. Through messaging systems, networks are created between individuals or groups and data is shared. Books are acquired through the online medium.

Objectives achieved by the process of knowledge transfer through internet

1. The content uploaded and shared on the social media platforms constitutes to archival of the valuable content.
2. The interviews and knowledge sharing sessions conducted by different art related organisations have proven to be a treasure that provides data or leads to data aiding the process of research.
3. Resource persons could be reached out to from any part of the world.

Limitations of the process of knowledge transfer through the internet

1. During live streaming, there may be technical glitches
2. The level of comfort in the online medium is not the same for all. Bonding between individuals may take more time.
3. While the social media platforms provide a wider reach to the content, there is a certain amount of dependancy on the owners concerned.
4. The listener needs exposure to the theoretical knowledge of the rituals carried out under this tradition and the association of rāga-s with each ritual and each festival. This is possible by bringing the interviews and performances are on a single platform.

Summary

The content that is shared on the internet on the platform of social media has a wide reach that crosses the boundaries of communities and geographical locations. While this medium has proven to be powerful, the authenticity is in question in many of recordings that are found on the internet platforms. This study has taken up the content created by two authentic performers of the Havēlī tradition - Sri Krishnadas Nayak and Sri Goswami Gokulotsav Maharaj. Practitioners who belong to the authentic tradition possess the ability to create valuable archives. Sri Krishnadas Nayakji is of the opinion that true practitioners are those who live this tradition and they need to share content on platforms that possess worldwide reach. Gokulotsav Maharajji in his online interview with Sri Ashok Mathur, welcomes skilled musicians to perform Havēlī Saṅgīta with the condition that this form is learnt by following authentic sources or Guru-s.

Dedicated platforms for the purpose of Havēlī Saṅgīta, with the content curated by experts would benefit the practitioners and would aid further research.

The online interactive teaching using video conferencing had seen increased demand during the pandemic. Havēlī Saṅgīta has not lagged behind in the attempt to adapt to this teaching medium. The online classes give freedom to the teacher to take sessions from anywhere, from the comfort of their home or in the premises of the temple. Here, though the opportunity has been created, serious learners are few in number (Krishnadas Nayak).

References

1. Bhai Baldeep Singh. "YaarAnād Virtual Baithak Mēlā S1: E37 with Dr. Pt. Gokulotsavji Maharaj". facebook, 24 May. 2020, <https://www.facebook.com/BhaiBaldeep/videos/280816343071676/>
2. Bindu K. "Impact of technology on music". University of Kerala.2013. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8443/jspui/handle/10603/413669>
3. Chabildas, Champaklal Nayak. Aṣṭa Chāpīya Bhakti Saṅgīta (Udbhava Aur Vikāsa), Parts 1-3. Ashta ChāpaKala Kendra, 1983.
4. Das Shambhavi, "Role of media and technology in Indian Classical Music", <https://www.academia.edu/32848113>
5. Ganga-Jamuni. "A talk on Pushtimarg and Haveli Sangeet by Padma Bhushan Acharya Dr. Pandit Gokulotsavji Maharaj". facebook, 10 September. 2020, <https://www.facebook.com/gangajamuniheritage/videos/319972343397662/>

6. "Raag Seva of the Divine - Haveli Sangeet" facebook, 1 October. 2020, <https://www.facebook.com/gangajamuniheritage/videos/810051769769168/>
7. Nayak, Krishnadas. Teaching online and use of internet technology for the propagation of Puṣṭi Mārgīya Saṅgīta. Personal Interview. 25 July 2023.
8. Krishnadas-Pushtivrund. "Krushnakumar Nayak's Personal Meeting Room". facebook, 7 May. 2021, <https://www.facebook.com/KrishnadasPushtivrund/videos/525877261755266/>
9. Kunte Chaitanya, "Media for promotion of Indian Classical Music", Swar Ganga Music Foundation, <https://www.swarganga.org/articles/details.php?id=13>
10. Pt. Gokulotsavji Maharaj. "Hindola Ke Pad Acharya Gokulotsavji Maharaj | Pushtimargiya Kirtan Haveli Sangeet". YouTube, 31 July. 2021, https://youtu.be/9pMK7GSasds?si=SFmQO_W9pjd5KF5e
11. Pushtivrund. "Aao Kirtan Sikhe || S01E05 || Raag: Sorath". YouTube, 17 Jun. 2020, <https://youtu.be/1eR1mpF5SFE?si=q5U2OoBiguMjGhxM>
12. "Aao Kirtan Sikhe || S01E07 || Learn How to Play Jhanj". YouTube, 8 July. 2020, <https://youtu.be/9oKUik30JTQ?si=qwzsdIHWxP6VaJIY>
13. "Aao Kirtan Sikhe || S01E08 || Basic Information of Taal Tevra & Chautal". YouTube, 14 July. 2020, <https://youtu.be/V68dNyf2BFg?si=6NVsq9RzKYhFjTJQ>
14. "Ari Maai Nai Nai Dharati Dulhani Hoy | Sehra Ko Pad | Varsaha Rutu | Gaud Malhar". YouTube, 5 August. 2023, <https://youtu.be/LSO0KUu5ZRI?si=hTO2uWWhxLntBvKs>
15. "Gaave Ghanashyam Jamuna ke Teera| Raga Gaud Malhar". YouTube, 17 August. 2023, <https://youtu.be/R5r5gYFqPnE?si=7vVoqZ67XQQD3Zu1>
16. "Raagmala- Taalmala | Hindora ke pad". YouTube, 21 August. 2021, <https://youtu.be/dp9RNxmsvWw?si=6I3aAnsK6Lz5BVK>
17. Ravishankar Sudha, Banerjee Neil, "An Analysis of audience engagement by Indian Classical Music artists and Dancers during lockdown via social media", Gap Bodhi Taru– Volume- IV, Issue – III, September 2021) pp.31-35, <https://www.gapbodhitaru.org/res/articles/Sudha.pdf>
18. Sharma, Satyabhan. Puṣṭi Mārgīya Mandiron Ki Saṅgīta Paramparā, Havēlī Saṅgīt. Radha Publication, 1999.
19. Vedabala Samidha, "Indian Classical Music in a Globalized World", Sangeet Galaxy Vol5, Issue-1, (January 2016)pp.3-9, <https://sangeetgalaxy.co.in/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/4597460703.IndianClassicalMusicintheglobalizedworld.pdf>

